

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Bacher****FIRST NAME: Annica****PROGRAM CODE: MIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma**

The author applied XUS UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author Xdid did not use Zotero to insert references

The author Xdid did not use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: MS Word 2013

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **Which of the following answers concerning quotations is NOT correct?**
 - A paraphrase is marked by italics.**¹
 - A direct quotation is indicated by quotation marks.
 - When information is considered common knowledge, a citation is not necessary.
 - A paraphrase restates the author's idea in your own words.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Bangui, Central African Republic: EUCLID University, 2019), 6-10.

2. **What is a style guide?**

- A documentation of an author's previous works.
- A means to improve an author's personal style.
- A manual ensuring consistent style of writing.**²
- A style guide is generally not useful to freelance writers.

3. **Which of the following statements concerning types of information is correct?**

- An interview with a survivor of World War II about his/her experiences is a secondary source.
- An article quoting an expert is a secondary source.**³
- A student's essay (e.g., response paper) is a primary source.
- A biased source is usually trustworthy.

4. **Which of the following statements concerning tables and figures is correct?**

- To compare one variable across a series of items, a pie chart is understandable.
- It is not acceptable to abbreviate large numbers in tables.
- The application of different colors and shades usually makes a table easier to read.
- Titles, enumerations, and short explanations are given directly**

² Ibid., 24-26.

³ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, *Write Source 2000* (Boston: Houghton Mifflin Company, 1999), 261-264.

next to a graphic.⁴

5. Why do researchers NOT cite sources?

- To appear as modest.**⁵
- To show research tradition.
- To assure the accuracy of facts.
- To help extend their research.

6. The reference of distinct types of sources focuses on particular details. Which of the following is NOT correct?

- When citing a website, an access date shall be given.
- When citing an online video (e.g., YouTube), the record studio must always be named.**⁶
- Always state the place of publication for books.
- If existing, the volume/issue number of a journal shall be specified.

7. Which of the following statements concerning titles of works (Turabian) is correct?

- You can change a title's punctuation to make it easier to read.
- Titles in foreign languages shall be capitalized headline-style.
- Titles of smaller works (e.g., journal article) are referenced in italics.

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013), 54-66.

⁵ Ibid., 86.

⁶ Ibid., 136-156.

- Always give a title exactly as it appears in the original.**⁷
8. **Block quotations are formatted differently in various styles. Which answer is correct?**
- In Harvard Style, quotation marks are used for block quotations.
- In Turabian, a quote of five lines and more is formatted as a block quotation.**⁸
- A reference can be omitted when giving a block quote.
- In WHO style, a quote of five lines and more is formatted as a block quotation.
9. **What is considered irrelevant information?**
- Critical background information.
- Reference to an author you cited.
- Reference to the people on your team.**⁹
- Introductory sentence stating the importance of your topic.
10. **Distinct differences part British and American English. Which of the following is correct?**
- In British English, single quotation marks are used for regular**

⁷ Ibid., 185-187.

⁸ Ibid., 209-210; Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 70; World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide* (Geneva, Switzerland: World Health Organization, 2004), 23.

⁹Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*, 6-8.

short citations.¹⁰

- In American English, no period is placed after “Mr”.
- The list “blue, yellow, and green” is correctly punctuated according to British English.
- American English: If a sentence ends with a direct quote, the period is placed inside the quotation marks. (Example: I told him, “I prefer the blue team.”)

¹⁰ Ibid., 75; Ibid., 91-92; Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 198; World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide*, 35.

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